

Anti-JC virus seroprevalence in a Spanish multiple sclerosis cohort JC virus seroprevalence in Spain

[Yolanda Aladro](#)^a · [Rodrigo Terrero](#)^a · [Marta Cerezo](#)^a · [Ricardo Ginestal](#)^b · [Lucía Ayuso](#)^c · [Virginia Meca-Lallana](#)^d · [Jorge Millán](#)^e · [Laura Borrego](#)^f · [Marisa Martínez-Ginés](#)^g · [Luisa Rubio](#)^c · [Clara de Andrés](#)^g · [Ambrosio Miralles](#)^h · [Cristina Guijarro](#)ⁱ · [Elena Rodríguez-García](#)^j · [José Manuel García-Dominguez](#)^k · [Carmen Muñoz-Fernández](#)^l · [Carlos López de Silanes](#)^m · [Mayra Gómez](#)ⁿ · [Israel Thuissard](#)^o · [María Cerdán](#)^{p,q} · [Itziar Palmí](#)^d · [Luis Felipe Díaz-Garzón](#)ⁱ · [Jose Meca-Lallana](#)^{p,q} [Show less](#)

Affiliations

- ^aMultiple Sclerosis Unit, Department of Neurology, Getafe University Hospital, European University of Madrid, Spain
- ^bDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Fundación Jiménez Díaz”, Madrid, Spain
- ^cDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Príncipe de Asturias”, Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain
- ^dDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “La Princesa”, Madrid, Spain
- ^eDepartment of Neurology, General Hospital “La Mancha Centro”, Alcázar de San Juan, Ciudad Real, Spain
- ^fDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Fundación de Alcorcón”, Madrid, Spain
- ^gDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Gregorio Marañón”, Madrid, Spain
- ^hDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Infanta Sofía”, San Sebastián de los Reyes, Madrid, Spain
- ⁱDepartment of Neurology, Hospital “Santa Bárbara”, Puertollano, Ciudad Real, Spain
- ^jDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Severo Ochoa”, Leganés, Madrid, Spain
- ^kDepartment of Neurology, Hospital Central de la Defensa “Gómez Ulla”, Madrid, Spain
- ^lDepartment of Neurology, Hospital Complex Torrecárdenas, Almería, Spain
- ^mDepartment of Neurology, Torrejon University Hospital, Madrid, Spain

- nDepartment of Neurology, University Hospital “Infanta Leonor”, Madrid, Spain
- oDepartment of Statistics, European University of Madrid, Spain
- pDepartment of Neurology, MS Unit, University Clinic Hospital “Virgen de la Arrixaca” (IMIB-Arrixaca), Murcia, Spain
- qCátedra de Neuroinmunología Clínica y Esclerosis Múltiple, UCAM, Universidad Católica San Antonio de Murcia, Spain

Highlights

- The seroprevalence of anti-JCV antibodies in Spanish MS patients' cohort was between 55.3 and 60.5%.
- Seroprevalence JCV only increased with age and when 2nd generation ELISA was employed.
- The seroconversion rate was 7% per year.
- Changes in serostatus were observed in 8% of our patients.
- Fluctuations on serological status were associated with antibody index near to assay's cut-off.

Abstract

Objective

To estimate the seroprevalence of anti-JCV antibodies, seroconverting rates and evolution of antibody levels in a multiple sclerosis (MS) Spanish cohort.

Methods

Multicenter, retrospective cross-sectional and longitudinal study. The JCV seroprevalence was analyzed in 711 MS patients by using 1st (STRATIFY-1) and 2nd generation (STRATIFY-2) two-step ELISA over 2.65 (± 0.97) years. Seroconversion rate was obtained over 2 samples from 314 patients, and index stability from 301 patients with 3 or more samples available. The effect of each ELISA generation, demographics, clinical characteristics and therapy on seroprevalence was assessed by logistic regression.

Results

The overall anti-JCV seroprevalence was 55.3% (51.6–58.9), similar across regions ($p=0.073$). It increased with age ($p<0.000$) and when STRATIFY-2 was used

(60.5%, $p=0.001$). Neither sex nor immunosuppressive therapy had any influence. Yearly seroconversion rate was 7% (considering only STRATIFY-2). Serological changes were observed in 24/301 patients, 5.7% initially seropositive reverted to seronegative and 7% initially seronegative changed to seropositive and again to seronegative, all these cases had initial index values around the assay's cut-off.

Conclusions

JCV seroprevalence in Spanish MS patients was similar to that reported in other European populations. Changes in serostatus are not infrequent and should be considered in clinical decisions.